

MODERATION OF ARCHITECTURAL INNOVATIONS

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Annotation: The article examines the issue of manifestations of creative innovations in traditional, mainly medieval Russian architecture. Various degrees of liberties taken in relation to the reproduction of architectural samples are revealed.

Key words: architectural designs, styles, traditions, innovation, creativity, subordination, regulation, freedom.

Introduction. In 2019, the entire architectural world celebrated the 100th anniversary of the famous Bauhaus, which played an equally significant role in the development of modern architecture in general and in our country especially. Many star architects of today admit that they were indelibly impressed by the masterpieces of the Soviet avant-garde. This flatters both practitioners and historians of Russian architecture of the twentieth century [1, 3].

However, it must be admitted that innovative architecture is not very close and pleasant to the general public, as, indeed, all other types of avant-garde art. Experts try to explain this by the deep conceptuality of such art and the insufficient preparedness of viewers to perceive it. There are calls not to hastily judge the talent of authors - it will certainly reveal itself over time [2, 4, 5]. But is it possible to prohibit judging art at first sight?

After all, this is so important! A reasonable question arises: can only architectural revelations permanently arise within the framework of an innovative

direction once discovered? And how can we generally evaluate innovation in relation to innovation without generally accepted criteria?

The avant-garde as a protest futurist movement opened up exciting prospects, but then, naturally, began to turn into a tradition with its own rules and dogmas. In a very tough and aggressive, it must be said, tradition, which can be called anti-tradition [7, 8, 9].

Today we are seeing attempts to imitate the buildings and projects of the Soviet avant-garde or the global modern movement, but the consistent development of some great and fundamentally new architectural language is not happening. Like the notorious artificial universal language Esperanto, it is rejected and reborn into something completely different - into exclusive experiments with a variety of forms, compositions, styles and their hybrids. Often, experiments are aimless and unceremonious in relation to the current environment [6, 10, 11].

At the same time, anti-globalist sentiments reinforce a rather serious interest in heritage, ethno-confessional traditions, and in the search for regional and local identity [12, 13, 14]. However, in practice, in such a “game” atmosphere of mass culture, the result is an unconvincing and sometimes deliberately shocking mixture of the ancient and the newfangled, the familiar and the frightening, one’s own and someone else’s.

In order to understand at least a little about the designated range of issues, it is useful to immerse yourself in history, full of both conservative customs and revolutionary impulses. Since ancient times, construction was almost universally practiced according to a well-known model, or in its likeness, as they said in Rus'. This kind of creative activity, conditioned by pre-established rules and models, is well suited to the term “craft”. The masters of the Middle Ages basically positioned themselves this way, fearing manifestations of self-thinking and pride. The main architectural examples were under the jurisdiction of princes, kings and high priests. Imitating them, local authorities, private owners and the construction

crews they hired quite consciously went to simplify forms and decorative decoration, reduce the scale, reduce the cost of building materials, etc.

Everyone had to know their place and not pretend that they were “beyond their rank.” From here came the stable traditionalism of art and culture of patriarchal society, which continued to exist in the conditions of the establishment of statehood and monotheistic religions.

Due to the noted orderly subordination, following the same patterns never led to the mechanistic reproduction of standard solutions. In addition, each traditional building certainly had to have its own unique personality.

Why is this so if the architects had no artistic ambitions? The answer to this question lies in the essence of the dominant religious, objective-idealistic consciousness. Without God's help, people could not imagine building even a very insignificant building. The forms and designs of the exemplary building not only told the craftsmen what and how to do, they helped them to capture the spiritual power of the eternal great image standing behind them, to join it, to receive a life-giving particle of this power and to invest it in a new creation. Therefore, about each traditional building we can say that it had its own soul, name and face.

Construction, like any serious craft, was spiritual, and therefore creative in the best sense of the word.

Despite the inviolability of the foundations of traditional culture, very unusual, namely innovative works of architecture sometimes appeared within its framework. They stood out noticeably from the rest with their bright individual expressiveness, which testified to their special status and their commemoration of some new milestone in the course of history. These outstanding works became new models and sources of inspiration for subsequent imitators.

Their birth could not have been accidental. This had to be the will of God and, of course, the command of the first persons of the church and state. The masters called to such a great task also used famous examples, but this time with the goal of exceeding their significance and beauty. Here we were talking not

about resemblance to a model, but about using it as a creative aid. Architects had to be especially gifted people, worthy of insight into the higher spheres. The hierarchical picture of the world remained the same, only the spiritual movement in it was not directed as usual - from top to bottom, but, on the contrary, upward.

Abstractionism, nihilistic in relation to the historical heritage, over time began to seem like just one of the leftist artistic movements, almost like a style in which one can continue to work. Modernism grew out of it. But the fundamental intentions of the futurist innovators were completely different, namely: in the destruction of all stylistic and exemplary shackles and achieving the complete victory of free, reckless, ahistorical creativity.

It's as if the flow of history ends and an eternal world of universal prosperity begins. This is the secret of the special attractiveness of the avant-garde of the first quarter of the twentieth century, that its innovative ideas seem inexhaustible, timeless and endlessly flowing, as if from a cornucopia.

But the miracle did not happen, and man never created a real paradise on earth with his own hands. Instead of styleless form-creation, the game of historical architectural models unfolded with renewed vigor, receiving exaggerated scale and expression. And after that, the course abruptly changed to mass industrial construction according to standard projects, which provided good savings on architectural innovations and delights. The main postulate was the requirement to rationalize architectural design as much as possible, following scientific and technological progress. Innovation was liberated from fundamental architectural content in favor of "technical aesthetics."

The pulse of professionals still beat, painfully reacting to the faceless and ugly architecture. Individual more or less original projects and buildings appeared, of course, not thanks to, but in spite of the existing system.

A quick excursion into history shows that genuine architectural creativity has always contained something new and unique. But adherence to tradition forced the emergence of innovations to be strictly dosed. Persons of the highest social

status had the greatest power to innovate. Only they could change samples and demand from architects something more than what everyone was used to. And they were responsible for their decisions. At the same time, their freedom of expression was by no means unlimited; it was controlled by society itself, its cultural norms and customs.

The current Town Planning Code requires that design decisions be carried out through public hearings. This is the right step towards the rehabilitation of the traditional order of things. He should not be underestimated. The profession really needs to restore direct and backward connections with society. It is not without reason that in developed countries the “participatory method” is cultivated, obliging architects and other specialists to work in the interests of residents. Another thing is that we must not slide into populism. It is necessary to observe a sense of proportion in everything. Unfortunately, today all the successes and failures of architects are based mainly on their personal business and human qualities. Individualism and hypertrophied – “breakthrough” – creativity are overly encouraged. However, the levels of talent and skill are not actually ranked. This leads to the fact that something untenable can be passed off as a professional achievement, and meaningless design originality can be passed off as an architectural innovation. The cult of innovation that emerged in the 20th century does us a disservice. Is innovation put on stream capable of generating a sustainable increase in the quality of architecture? Of course not. Unfortunately, there is a movement in the opposite direction.

Conclusions. Serious difficulties in creating and perceiving works of architecture are associated with the destruction of the once harmonious system of cultural values and landmarks, a decrease in the overall level of assessment of architectural and artistic achievements and the spread, under the slogans of equality and freedom, of excessive subjectivism and pluralistic permissiveness demoralizing society. In contrast to this, I would like to propose expanding the vector of innovative searches from the notorious breakthroughs into the unknown

to the creation of newly stable and benign traditions that would be accepted by society and live, consistently develop, allowing the emergence of innovations, only moderate and delicate ones. This will help the much-needed harmonization of different time and different quality elements of the urban, suburban, rural and natural environment.

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